

Analyzing Translation Strategies for Allah's Attributes in the Holy Qur'an

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ABSTRACT

The translation of proper nouns, such as Allah's attributes of acts, has consistently been a contentious issue in the translation of Qur'anic exegesis. This research aimed to investigate the frequency and types of strategies employed in the English translations of Allah's attributes of acts in the Holy Qur'an. The study sought to explore the strategies used by translators in the translation of Qur'anic exegesis and to determine if significant differences existed among the translators in the application of the strategies proposed by Chesterman (1997). The corpus comprised six English translations of the Holy Qur'an by Asad, Pickthall, Saheeh, Arberry, Khan and Hilali, and Mubarakpuri. Both descriptive and inferential statistics were utilized to analyze the data, based on a revised version of Chesterman's (1997) model. The descriptive data revealed that only six out of ten strategies were used in translating Allah's attributes of acts. Only two strategies, transposition and emphasis change, were not used significantly differently, while the other four strategies, synonymy, paraphrase, transliteration, and expansion, were employed significantly differently. The inferential statistics revealed significant differences in the application of each strategy by each translator. However, no significant differences were found among the translators in the application of the same strategy when rendering Allah's attributes of acts.

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1. Introduction

According to Farahani (2013), more than eighty percent of the approximately 1.5 billion Muslim population do not know Arabic and rely on translations to understand the meanings and messages of the Holy Qur'ān. As the Holy Qur'ān is the most widely read book in human history and a source of immense inspiration, guidance, and wisdom for millions of Muslims worldwide (Qadri, 2007, p. 2), it is necessary to pay close attention to how Qur'ānic translations are conducted. Currently, one of the significant challenges in the field of translation is the translation of proper nouns (Farahzad, 1995, Mirza Suzani, 2009). Translating proper nouns, such as Allah's attributes of acts, often poses a major problem in the translation of Qur'ānic exegesis. Numerous models have been proposed for the translation of proper nouns, but none seem to be comprehensive, and they may not cover all the strategies employed by translators. Soltez (1967) divides proper nouns into three types: sign names, word names, and combined names. Sign names are non-descriptive, non-connotative, and unmotivated, having no meaning in the way a common noun does. Word names are motivated, connotative, and mostly descriptive, while combined names are combinations of sign names and elements from common word classes. Alternatively, Newmark (1988, pp. 214-216) categorizes proper nouns into three groups:

- People's names: These are typically transferred, preserving their nationality, and assuming that their names have no connotations in the text.
- Names of objects: These consist of trademarks, brands, or proprietaries.
- Geographical terms: Translators must stay up-to-date in their rendering, check all terms in the most recent atlas or gazetteer, and where necessary, consult with the concerned embassies. They must respect a country's wish to determine its own choice of names for its geographical features.

Given these considerations, selecting an appropriate model is crucial for identifying suitable strategies for the translation of proper nouns. This research aimed to examine the type and frequency of strategies applied in English translations of Allah's attributes of acts in the Holy Qur'ān. It sought to explore the strategies used by translators in translating Qur'ānic exegesis and to determine if there were significant differences among the translators in the application of the strategies proposed by Chesterman (1997). For this purpose, six English translations of the Holy Qur'ān by Asad, Pickthall, Saheeh, Arberry, Khan and Hilali, and Mubarakpuri were considered, and a revised version of Chesterman's (1997) model was used to analyze the data.

In terms of pedagogical significance, it is anticipated that professionals, educators, students, and aspiring translators can benefit from the proposed model and the findings of this study. With this in mind, the study aims to explore the following research questions:

1. What are the most and least frequently employed strategies by the six translators when translating Allah's Attributes of Acts from Arabic into English?
2. Are there any statistically significant differences among the translators in the utilization of each strategy?
3. Are there any statistically significant differences among the translators in the application of the same strategy when translating the same Allah's Attribute of Acts?

2. Review of Literature

Translating proper nouns, such as the attributes of acts of Allah, often poses a significant challenge for translators of sacred texts, as they strive to maintain the sanctity of these nouns. Despite the existence of numerous models for translating proper nouns, none seem to be comprehensive, and they may not cover all the strategies employed by translators. Therefore, identifying suitable strategies for translating proper nouns is deemed an important prerequisite.

In his study, Abu-Mahfouz (2011) investigated problems and semantic issues related to nouns. The study found that these problems arose for at least three reasons: the translator used synonyms, transliterated words that had straightforward equivalents, and translated words that required translation.

Al-Omar (2013) explored the complexities and implications of transliterating proper nouns between Arabic and English. To address the challenges of translating proper nouns, Al-Omar suggested a set of conventionalized rules. The study showed that it might be sufficient for language purists to establish some transliteration guidelines for translators. The translator's awareness of the facts and implications of the differences between the two languages helped them avoid inconsistencies, which could negatively impact the linguistic intuition of the native speakers of both languages.

Chrestensen (2014) focused on the translation of compound nouns in user manuals in his study. He investigated the translation strategies used for these compound nouns. The study, which was based on two empirical studies, showed that respondents tended to prefer a direct form of translation over an explanation, and translators generally did well when translating compound nouns.

Thanh (2014) studied the machine translation of proper names from English and French into Vietnamese. This study focused on the problems of English-Vietnamese and French-Vietnamese proper noun machine translation systems. The findings showed that the pre-processing solution significantly reduced proper noun machine translation errors and contributed to the improvement of the machine translation systems for Vietnamese.

In a study on the translation of proper names in Iran, Mirza Suzani (2008) examined the challenges of translating proper names from English to Persian and suggested some potential approaches. Similarly, in his book "Translation of Simple Texts", Mirza Suzani (2009) presented a variety of classifications of proper nouns in English, considering social, cultural, historical, and geopolitical aspects, and proposed various Persian equivalents.

In another study, Abdolmaleki (2012) explored what happens to proper names in the process of translation, particularly from English into Persian. The study concluded that it was not accurate to simply claim that proper nouns were untranslatable. Instead, they sometimes needed to be translated, sometimes directly transformed, and sometimes coupled with definitions, all depending on their specific characteristics and the context in which they were used.

Ahanizadeh (2012) investigated the translation of proper names in children's literature. The study was based on Van Coillie's (2006) model of translation strategies of proper nouns. After extracting and comparing all proper nouns from twenty-five English books and their

Persian translations, the study found that the strategy of “reproduction” was the most commonly used in translating proper names from English into Persian.

3. Methodology

3.1. Materials

In this study, the Noble Qur’ān was selected as the primary source for data collection. This Holy Book is considered the most significant religious text and the principal source of Allah’s Attributes of Acts. Furthermore, a variety of well-annotated English translations of this sacred text are readily available, along with its original Arabic version. In this study, forty of Allah’s Attributes of Acts were identified with the assistance of clerics (see Appendix 1). Additionally, several major relevant sources were consulted to ensure that virtually no attributes of acts were overlooked.

3.2. Analytical Model

In this study, a revised version of Chesterman’s (1997) taxonomy for translation strategies served as the theoretical framework. This model was chosen as the foundation of the study’s framework because it encompasses 28 translation strategies, making it a nearly comprehensive model for translating proper nouns. However, due to certain limitations, several overlapping, redundant, or less relevant strategies were excluded, particularly those focusing on sentence translation rather than noun translation. To enhance the framework’s comprehensiveness, two additional strategies were incorporated, one from Farahzad (1995) and another from Newmark (1998). Consequently, a revised version of Chesterman’s (1997) model, comprising ten strategies, was established. The types of strategies in the revised version of Chesterman’s (1997) model were presented as follows:

Here’s a revised version of your text:

Literal Translation: Chesterman (1997) defines this as a strategy where the translator adheres as closely as possible to the form of the source text, without strictly following the structure of the source language.

Loan Translation: This refers to the borrowing of individual terms and adhering to the structure of the source text, which may be foreign to the target reader (Chesterman, 1997).

Transposition: Borrowed from Vinay and Darbelnet (1958) by Chesterman (1997), this term refers to any change in word class, such as from an adjective to a noun.

Synonymy: In this strategy, the translator selects the closest alternative term with the same meaning, which is not the first literal translation of the source text word or phrase (Chesterman, 1997).

Antonymy: Chesterman (1997) explains this strategy as one where the translator uses a word with the opposite meaning, often combined with a negation.

Hyponymy: This involves using a member of a larger category (e.g., ‘rose’ is a hyponym in relation to ‘flower’). Conversely, a hypernym is a related superordinate term that describes the entire category with a broader term (e.g., ‘flower’ is a hypernym in relation to ‘rose’) (Chesterman, 1997).

Paraphrase: According to Chesterman (1997), this strategy involves creating a liberal approximate translation based on the overall meaning of the source text, where some lexical items may be modified or ignored.

Emphasis Change: Chesterman (1997) states that this strategy involves increasing, decreasing, or changing the emphasis of the thematic focus of the translated text compared to the original.

Transliteration: Farahzad (1995) explains that transliteration and transcription are used for translating personal proper names. Transliteration occurs when the letter of the target language represents the pronunciation of the Proper Noun (PN) in the source language, while transcription involves replacing one letter of the alphabet in the source language (SL) with another letter in the target language (TL) (p.43).

Expansion: Newmark (1998) defines expansion as a strategy that involves adding elements in translation.

3.3. Data Collection and Analysis

The following procedures were undertaken to conduct this study. Initially, the Holy Qur'ān in Arabic was used as the primary source for data collection. Subsequently, six English translations of the Holy Qur'ān were procured. These translations included renditions by Muhammad Marmaduke Pickthall (1930), Muhammad Asad (1980), Arthur Arberry (1955), Muhammad Sarwar (1981), Muhammad Mohsin Khan and Muhammad Taqi-ud-Din Al-Hilali (1999), and Saheeh International (2007). These renditions served as the data source from which the English equivalents of Allah's Attributes of Acts were identified. In total, forty of Allah's Attributes of Acts in Arabic were identified as the study corpus (refer to Appendix 1), and their English equivalents were extracted. A revised version of Chesterman's (1997) model was employed to analyze the data while translating the forty Allah's Attributes of Acts from Arabic into English. All strategies applied by the translators were noted, and the frequency of each strategy was recorded. Chi-square tests were run to determine the significance of differences between the strategies used by the translators. The collected data were then analyzed using SPSS software (version 24). To minimize rater errors during data analysis, inter-rater reliability was estimated. For this purpose, two raters participated in labeling the data. After labeling, the data were compared. A correlation of the labels revealed a reliability of 0.80 ($r=.80$) between the two raters. Finally, areas of discrepancy were discussed between the two raters to reduce inconsistencies.

4. Findings

In this study, both descriptive and inferential statistics were utilized for data analysis. The sample comprised 40 items, each rendered by six different English translators. Furthermore, based on the applied framework, ten distinct strategies were identified, as detailed in Table 1.

Table 1. Analytical Strategies Employed for Data Analysis

No.	Strategy
I	Literal translation
II	Loan translation
III	Transposition

No.	Strategy
IV	Synonymy
V	Antonymy
VI	Hyponymy
VII	Paraphrase
VIII	Emphasis change
IX	Transliteration
X	Expansion

In Table 2, the frequency and percentage of the strategies applied by translators during the rendition of Allah's Attributes of Acts from Arabic into English have been reported. Data on each translator's rendition is presented individually and the frequency and percentage of all strategies are reported for each translator.

Table 2. Frequency and Percentage of Strategies Utilized by Asad

Strategy	Frequency	Percentage
Transposition	2	5
Synonymy	14	35
Paraphrase	18	45
Emphasis change	1	2.5
Expansion	5	12.5
Total	40	100

Table 2 reveals that Asad most frequently employed Strategy VII, paraphrasing, with 18 instances accounting for 45% of the total. The second most common strategy was Strategy IV, synonymy, used 14 times, making up 35% of the total. Strategy X, expansion, was the third most used, with 5 instances representing 15.5%. Asad utilized Strategy III, transposition, twice (5%), and Strategy VIII, emphasis change, just once (2.5%), making them the least used strategies. Asad did not use any of the other strategies.

Table 3. Frequency and Percentage of Strategies Utilized by Pickthall

Strategy	Frequency	Percentage
Synonymy	31	77.5
Paraphrase	5	12.5
Expansion	4	10
Total	40	100

Table 3 shows that Pickthall used Strategy IV (synonymy) more than any other strategy, with 31 instances (77.5%). The second and third most common strategies were Strategy VII (paraphrase) and Strategy X (expansion), with 5 (12.5%) and 4 (10%) occurrences, respectively. Pickthall did not use any of the other strategies.

According to Table 4, Saheeh used Strategy IV (synonymy) most frequently, with 30 instances (75%). The next four most used strategies were Strategy VII (paraphrase), Strategy X (expansion), Strategy VIII (emphasis change), and Strategy IX (transliteration), with 4 (10%), 3 (7.5%), 2 (5%), and 1 (2.5%) occurrences, respectively. Saheeh did not use any other strategies.

Table 4. Frequency and Percentage of Strategies Utilized by Saheeh

Strategy	Frequency	Percentage
Synonymy	30	75
Paraphrase	4	10
Emphasis change	2	5
Transliteration	1	2.5
Expansion	3	7.5
Total	40	100

Table 5 reveals that Arberry used Strategy IV (synonymy) more than half of the time, with 21 instances (52.5%). The next most common strategy was Strategy X (expansion), with 17 occurrences (42.5%). Strategy VII (paraphrase) was the least used strategy by Arberry, with only one instance (2.5%). Arberry did not employ any other strategies.

Table 5. Frequency and Percentage of Strategies Utilized by Arberry

Strategy	Frequency	Percentage
Synonymy	21	52.5
Paraphrase	2	5
Expansion	17	42.5
Total	40	100

Table 6 shows that Khan and Hilali used Strategy IV (synonymy) most often, with 18 instances (45%). The other five strategies they used were Strategy VII (paraphrase), Strategy X (expansion), Strategy VIII (emphasis change), Strategy III (transposition), and Strategy IX (transliteration), with 10 (25%), 6 (15%), 4 (10%), 1 (2.5%), and 1 (2.5%) occurrences, respectively. They did not use any other strategies.

Table 6. Frequency and Percentage of the Strategies Utilized by Khan and Hilali

Strategy	Frequency	Percentage
Transposition	1	2.5
Synonymy	18	45
Paraphrase	10	25
Emphasis change	4	10
Transliteration	1	2.5
Expansion	6	15
Total	40	100

Table 7 shows that Mubarakpuri used Strategy IV (synonymy) and Strategy IX (transliteration) equally, with 12 instances (30%) each. The next two most common strategies were Strategy X (expansion) and Strategy VIII (emphasis change), with 6 (15%) and 5 (12.5%) occurrences, respectively. Strategy VII (paraphrase) and Strategy III (transposition) were the least used strategies by Mubarakpuri, with 4 (10%) and 1 (2.5%) instances, respectively. He did not employ any of the other four strategies in the model framework.

Table 7. Frequency and Percentage of the Strategies Utilized by Mubarakpuri

Strategy	Frequency	Percentage
Transposition	1	2.5
Synonymy	12	30
Paraphrase	4	10
Emphasis change	5	12.5
Transliteration	12	30
Expansion	6	15
Total	40	100

To answer the second research question, chi-square tests were conducted to examine the differences in the frequencies of the strategies used by different translators. Tables 8 present the results of the chi-square tests for each strategy employed by each translator.

Table 8 shows that the strategies used by Asad differed significantly in their frequencies ($p < 0.05$). Strategy VII (paraphrase) was the most common strategy used by Asad, based on the observed frequencies.

Table 8. Chi-Square Test Results for Various Strategies Used by Asad

Strategy	Observed N	Expected N	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Transposition	2	8.0	28.750	4	.000
Synonymy	14	8.0			
Paraphrase	18	8.0			
Emphasis change	1	8.0			
Expansion	5	8.0			
Total	40				

Table 9 reveals that the strategies used by Pickthall varied significantly in their frequencies ($p < 0.05$). Strategy IV (synonymy) was the most frequent strategy used by Pickthall, based on the observed frequencies.

Table 9. Chi-Square Test for Various Strategies Used by Pickthall

Strategy	Observed N	Expected N	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Synonymy	31	13.3	35.150	2	.000
Paraphrase	5	13.3			
Expansion	4	13.3			
Total	40				

Table 10. Chi-Square Test for Various Strategies Used by Saheeh

Strategy	Observed N	Expected N	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Synonymy	30	8.0	76.250	4	.000
Paraphrase	4	8.0			
Emphasis change	2	8.0			
Transliteration	1	8.0			
Expansion	3	8.0			
Total	40				

Table 10 indicates that the strategies used by Saheeh had significantly different frequencies ($p < 0.05$). Strategy IV (synonymy) was the most common strategy used by Saheeh, compared to the other four strategies.

Table 11 shows that the frequencies of the strategies used by Arberry were significantly different ($P < 0.05$). Strategy IV (synonymy) was the most frequent strategy used by Arberry, compared to the other strategies.

Table 11. Chi-Square Test for Various Strategies Used by Arberry

Strategy	Observed N	Expected N	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Synonymy	21	13.3	15.050	2	.001
Paraphrase	2	13.3			
Expansion	17	13.3			
Total	40				

Table 12 indicates that the strategies used by Khan and Hilali differed significantly in their frequencies ($P < 0.05$). Strategy IV (synonymy) was the most common strategy used by Khan and Hilali, based on the observed frequencies.

Table 12. Chi-Square Test for Various Strategies Used by Khan and Hilali

Strategy	Observed N	Expected N	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Transposition	1	6.7	31.700	5	.000
Synonymy	18	6.7			
Paraphrase	10	6.7			
Emphasis change	4	6.7			
Transliteration	1	6.7			
Expansion	6	6.7			
Total	40				

Table 13 indicates that the strategies used by Mubarakpuri had significantly different frequencies ($p < 0.05$). Mubarakpuri used Strategy IV (synonymy) and Strategy IX (transliteration) more often than the other strategies, based on the observed frequencies.

Table 13. Chi-Square Test for Various Strategies Used by Mubarakpuri

Strategy	Observed N	Expected N	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Transposition	1	6.7	14.900	5	.011
Synonymy	12	6.7			
Paraphrase	4	6.7			
Emphasis change	5	6.7			
Transliteration	12	6.7			
Expansion	6	6.7			
Total	40				

To answer the third research question, another chi-square test was conducted to examine the differences among the translators in using the same strategy for translating the same Allah's Attribute of Act. Table 14 presents the results of this chi-square test.

Table 14 shows that the six translators did not differ significantly in using the same strategy for translating the same Allah's Attribute of Act ($p > 0.05$). This means that these translators used a common strategy for translating a given Attribute, based on the statistical analysis.

Table 14. Comparison of Translators' Application of The Same Strategy When Translating the Same Attribute of An Act at Different Levels

Level	Observed N	Expected N	Chi-Square	Df	Sig.
1	18	10.2	8.314	4	.081
2	9	10.2			
3	10	10.2			
4	8	10.2			
5	6	10.2			
Total	51				

5. Discussion and Conclusion

This study examined the frequencies of translation strategies used by six translators when rendering Allah's Attributes of Acts from Arabic into English. It also explored potential statistically significant differences among translators in their applications of distinct strategies and whether consistent strategies were used to translate the same Attributes across translators. The analysis adopted a revised version of Chesterman's (1997) model.

Based on the results obtained, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- Each translator employed different strategies significantly while translating Allah's Attributes of Acts.
- Asad used strategy VII (paraphrase) significantly more frequently than other strategies, while Pickthall used strategy IV (synonymy) the most.
- Saheeh used strategy IV (synonymy) significantly more frequently than the other strategies, and made the least use of strategy IX (transliteration).
- Arbery used strategy IV (synonymy) significantly more frequently than other strategies, and strategy VII (paraphrase) the least.
- Khan and Hilali used strategies IV (synonymy) and IX (transliteration) significantly more frequently than other strategies, and made the least use of strategies III (transposition) and IX (transliteration).
- Mubarakpuri employed strategies IV (synonymy) and IX (transliteration) significantly more frequently than other strategies, and made the least use of strategy III (transposition).
- Translators used strategies III (transposition) and VIII (emphasis change) in a similar way, with no significant difference among the six translators in the application of the same strategy while translating the same Allah's Attribute of Act.

- While all translators used similar strategies to translate Allah's Attributes of Acts, only Khan and Hilali and Mubarakpuri employed the maximum variety of strategies (six), while Pickthall and Arberry used the minimal variety of strategies (three).
- Strategies III (transposition), VIII (emphasis change), and IX (transliteration) were never used by Pickthall and Arberry, and strategies III (transposition) and IX (transliteration) were not employed by Saheeh and Asad, respectively.

Based on the results, it was evident that each translator employed the strategies with varying frequencies when translating these attributes. In essence, no single translator used similar frequencies of the strategies when rendering Allah's Attributes of Acts. This finding is consistent with Amjad et al.'s (2013) study on the strategies used for rendering divine names, where they found that each translator employed a strategy more frequently than others, indicating differing adoption levels of each translation strategy. Similarly, in the current study, strategy IV (synonymy), for example, was favored by four out of six translators.

The implications of the study are as follows. The study revealed the need for revisions to Chesterman's model of translating proper nouns (1997) in order to enrich the data collection and analysis procedures. The addition of the strategies of transliteration and expansion to the framework proposed by Chesterman reflects the ongoing need for eclecticism in the selection and revision of models and frameworks to enhance the translation process. The findings of the study may be valuable for other researchers conducting new research in this area. Additionally, the results could be beneficial to teachers and professors specializing in translation studies, as they may provide specific assistance in the translation of sacred texts. Furthermore, the findings of this study could be helpful for students preparing for practical translation activities and familiarize them with the most applicable strategies for translating Allah's names in the Holy Qur'ān.

The present research, similar to other studies in translation studies, has certain limitations. Despite the comprehensive efforts made by the researcher, several limitations were encountered. The study employed Chesterman's model of translating proper nouns (1997) as its framework, but other researchers may opt for different models suitable for their studies. Additionally, time constraints limited the use of multiple models, which could have enriched the data and improved the results. The research only focused on 40 attributes of Allah, and a larger selection could have enhanced the generalizability of the findings. Due to time constraints, only six English translations of the Holy Qur'ān were included in the study. A more extensive investigation involving a greater number of translators could have been conducted with more time available. The study solely examined translations from Arabic to English. Given more time, the researcher would have explored translations from other language pairs, such as Arabic to Persian. Other researchers may also investigate different language pairs and conduct studies from various perspectives on different aspects and features of proper names in their research. Future investigations could delve into other variables such as gender, translators' religious, (socio)cultural, and ideological backgrounds, and explore diverse genres beyond religious texts. These limitations highlight areas for potential expansion and improvement in future research endeavors in the field of translation studies.

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No	Attributes	Mubarakpuri	Khan and Hilali	Arberry	Saheeh	Pickthall	Asad
19	الكريم	Bountiful, The Most Generous	Bountiful, The Most Generous	All-Generous	The Generous	Bountiful	Most generous in giving, Bountiful
20	الرقيب	Watcher	Watcher	Watcher	Observer	Watcher	keeper
21	الشهيد	Witness	Witness	witness	Witness	Witness	witness
22	الوكيل	Disposer of Affairs	Disposer of Affairs	guardian	Disposer	Defender	guardian
23	الولي	The Wali	The Wali (Helper, Supporter, Protector, etc.)	Protector	Protector	Protecting Friend	Protector
24	الحميد	Worthy of all praise	Worthy of all praise	All-laudable	The praiseworthy	The Owner of Praise	the One to whom all praise is due
25	العليم	All-knowing	All-knowing	All-knowing	Knowing	All-Wis	All-knowing
26	التواب	the One Who accepts repentance,	the One Who accepts repentance	the Relenting	the Accepting of repentance	the relenting,	the Acceptor of Repentance
27	العفو	Ever Pardoning	Ever Oft-Pardoning	All-pardoning	ever Pardoning	ever Forgiving	absolver of sins
28	الملك	Al-Malik	the King	the King	the Sovereign	the Sovereign Lord	the Sovereign Supreme
29	غالب	Allah has full power and control over His affairs	Allah has full power and control over His Affairs	God prevails in His purpose	Allah is predominant over His affair	Allah was predominant in His career	God always prevails in whatever be His purpose
30	الهادي	Guide(verb)	Guide(verb)	guide	guide	guide	guide
31	البديع	The Originator	The Originator	the Creator	Originator	The Originator	The Originator
32	خلاق	Supreme Creator	Supreme Creator	All-creator	the Creator	the Creator	the Creator
33	فاطر	Fatir, The Creator	The Originator	Originator	Creator	the Creator	Originator
34	فالق	Cleaver	Cleaver	One who splits	The cleaver	The Cleaver	the One who cleaves
35	حاکم	judge	judge	judge	judge	judge	judge
36	رب	Lord	Lord	Lord	Lord	Lord	Sustainer
37	حميد	Worthy of all praise	Worthy of all praise	the All-laudable	the Praiseworthy	the Owner of Praise	the One to whom all praise is due
38	حليم	Most-Forbearing	Most-Forbearing	All-clement	Forbearing	Clement	forbearing
39	شفيع	intercessor	intercessor	intercessor	intercessor	intercessor	intercede with Him
40	وهاب	the Bestower	the Bestower	the Giver	the Bestower	the Bestower	the [true] Giver of Gifts